

EXPLORING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE LEARNING MODALITIES TOWARDS ENHANCED TEACHER TRAINING

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Exploring the Effectiveness of Online Learning Modalities towards Enhanced Teacher Training

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Abstract

The growing adoption of online learning modalities in recent years has brought about a fundamental change in the educational landscape. The way students interact with information has been altered by the incorporation of digital technologies into traditional educational frameworks. Moreover, teacher preparation programs have also been greatly affected by this development. The purpose of this study is to determine and assess the effectiveness of online learning modality and to propose teacher training inputs. It is crucial to understand how effective online learning is to the professional growth of teachers as educational institutions around the world negotiate the rapid transition to digital platforms. This study provides significant insights on how well online learning is effective among students and how to prepare teacher programs. This study utilized the descriptive-comparative research design. It randomly selected 270 students and 44 teachers from the junior high school department of Adamson University. Results reveal that student respondents assessed online learning modality as moderately effective in terms of teaching presence, social and cognitive presence. The teacher respondents assessed online learning modality as highly effective in terms of teaching presence and cognitive presence, and moderately effective in terms of social presence.

Keywords: *online learning modalities, educational frameworks, effectiveness*

Introduction

Online learning has become an increasingly popular modality for education, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. This mode of learning offers flexibility in terms of location and time and has been found to be effective in various educational contexts. Online learning modalities is found to be more effective than traditional face-to-face instruction (Means et al., 2010). As an effective platform, online learning promotes student engagement and interaction. The environment provided students with opportunities to engage in collaborative learning activities, which led to higher levels of student interaction and engagement (Rovai et al., 2013). Online learning has emerged as a crucial tool for educational institutions and learners worldwide.

Online learning ensures the continuity of education when traditional in-person classes are not feasible due to pandemic. It allows students to continue their studies remotely, maintaining academic progress without compromising their safety and well-being (Nambiar, 2020). Online learning provides equitable access to education, particularly for students who face barriers such as geographical distance, physical disabilities, or lack of resources (Son et al., 2020). It enables learners to engage in educational activities regardless of their location, ensuring inclusive education opportunities for all. Online learning offers flexibility in terms of time and location allowing students to tailor their learning schedules to accommodate personal responsibilities or challenges imposed by the pandemic. It provides the convenience of accessing educational materials and participating in discussions from anywhere with an internet connection (Xie et al., 2020). Indeed, online learning proved to be an effective way of continuing education among learners and teachers, with easy and equitable access to education, and flexibility and convenience to all.

After the pandemic, teaching transitioned again to traditional face-to-face classroom. However, investment in online learning platforms has been highlighted. The importance of online learning modalities in teaching and learning processes and other educational purposes is greatly important to review and assess its effectiveness towards developing inputs. Thus, this study is aimed to assess the effectiveness of online learning modality among students and teachers in a selected university in Manila towards developing teacher training inputs which can be used for continuous delivery of effective instruction of teaching and learning through online modality. Additionally, the study sought to describe how online learning modalities can support the development of essential skills and competencies that teachers need to be successful in the classroom.

Online learning has become an increasingly popular and accessible mode of education in recent years. Technological advancements, the internet's growth, and the need for flexible and inclusive learning environments have driven this shift.

The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated the adoption of online learning modalities as educational institutions sought ways to continue providing education to students while adhering to public health guidelines. Students get to experience full online learning. Teachers also need to adapt to the new learning environment for students as quickly as possible.

Traditionally, classroom lectures have relied on in-person instruction, hands-on experiences, and direct interactions with students, mentors, and peers. In the researcher's perspective, online learning has helped in the continuity of learning. However, the shift to online learning modalities has raised concerns about the effectiveness of online learning and the ability to prepare future educators adequately. At present, traditional face-to-face classes are back. However, it may be expected that online learning will be sustained. For this reason, this study hopes to prove the effectiveness of alternative learning modes.

Assessment of the effectiveness of online learning may answer some areas of the said modality among students and teachers. It is

important to assess its impact and effectiveness on the continuity of learning of students. Moreover, it can also be seen that teachers undeniably have experienced difficulties in adopting the online learning setup. After the assessment of the effectiveness of online learning, teacher training inputs may be proposed that may contribute to the overall quality and effectiveness of online learning and education. These inputs may include pedagogical approaches, course materials, practical experiences, mentorship opportunities, and assessment methods, among others.

Research Questions

The study assessed the effectiveness of online learning modality among students and teachers in a university. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the following respondents:
 - 1.1. student respondents;
 - 1.1.1 sex; and
 - 1.1.2 grade level?
 - 1.2. teacher respondents;
 - 1.2.1 educational attainment;
 - 1.2.2 years of teaching; and
 - 1.2.3 training on online learning?
 - 1.3. year level; and
 - 1.4. socio economic status?
2. What is the assessed effectiveness of online learning modality, in terms of:
 - 2.1. social presence;
 - 2.2. cognitive presence; and
 - 2.3. teaching presence;
3. Is there a significant difference in the assessed effectiveness of the online learning modality when the student respondents are grouped according to profile?
4. Is there a significant difference in the assessed effectiveness of the online learning modality when the teacher respondents are grouped according to profile?
5. Is there a significant difference between the assessed effectiveness of the online learning modality of student and teacher respondents?
6. What teacher training inputs may be proposed based on the result of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive-comparative research design was utilized in the study. The descriptive aspect was demonstrated by describing the profile of student respondents in terms of sex and grade level, and profile of teacher respondents in terms of educational attainment, years of teaching and training on online learning. More specifically, the descriptive method was used to assess the effectiveness of online learning of the study in terms of social presence, cognitive presence, and teaching presence. On the other hand, the comparative method was employed to investigate the difference between the effectiveness of online learning among student respondents and teacher respondents.

Respondents

The study employed stratified random sampling using Slovin's formula. The number of student respondents is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of Student Respondents according to Grade Level

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Total Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>
7	179	57
8	182	58
9	213	68
10	270	87
Total	844	270

$e = 0.05$

On the other hand, the population of teacher respondents has a total of 44. The sample size is the total number of teacher respondents.

Instruments

The survey instrument is composed of two parts. Part 1 focuses on the profile of the respondents and part 2 is on the effectiveness of the online learning modality which was adopted from the study of a developed instrument using Community of Inquiry Framework using a multi-institutional sample by Arbaugh et al., (2008) and utilized by Suharno et al., (2022). All 34 statements shall be considered consisting of 13 statements for teaching presence, 9 statements for social presence, and 12 statements for cognitive presence.

The survey questionnaire was answered using a Likert scale involving the expression of the respondents' level of agreement, or disagreement on a series of statements or questions. The scale involves four points, ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (4).

Procedure

The researcher administered the questionnaire face-to-face upon receipt of a formal approval letter from the university. The purpose and objectives of the study were explained by the researcher, including the instructions for the respondents. The confidentiality and voluntary nature of respondents' participation were likewise observed. The whole data gathering procedure took 10 – 15 minutes only.

The retrieval of accomplished questionnaires was done by the researcher. After the data were collated, the researcher encoded them to the computer software for analysis.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage) was used to describe the findings for the demographic profile of student and teacher respondents as for statement of the problem no. 1. Further statistical analyses were performed to determine the significant difference among the variables of the study.

All data were verified, coded, and transferred to the Excel spreadsheet, then encoded into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS v.29). Student's t-test and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was computed.

Mean was utilized to compute the average rating per category in assessing the effectiveness of online learning as for statement of problem no. 2. Mean was computed using SPSS. The mean score was described and interpreted according to the parameters set in Table 2.

Table 2. Weight Distribution and Verbal Interpretation of Mean Scores

Weight / Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.51 – 4.00	Highly Effective
3	2.51 – 3.50	Moderately Effective
2	1.51 – 2.50	Fairly Effective
1	1.00 – 1.50	Poorly Effective

Student's t-test was used to equate significance among two groups. On the other hand, analysis of variance (ANOVA) Comparison Test was utilized to compare two or more variables. T-Test and ANOVA were computed using SPSS. A statistically significant

0.05 level as considered. These tests were used to identify significant difference between student and teacher responses on the effectiveness of online learning as for statement of the problem nos. 3, 4 and 5.

Ethical Considerations

The study protocol was approved by the Adamson University Ethics Review Committee with protocol code number 2023-04-EDU-45. The researcher followed the informed consent and informed assent process. There were no risks in participating in this study. No incentives were given to respondents who joined. Without any obligations, the respondents can withdraw anytime from the study. For respondents 18 years and below, a co-signed informed assent form was required from the parents of the respondents. The researcher assured the understandability of the research process among children. No data were made identifiable to the respondents, to the university and to the community. Partial results were made available upon request. The researcher assured confidentiality of the identity of the respondents. All relevant information was kept private. Actual master and survey forms were kept for one year after the conclusion of the study and will be discarded afterwards. There is no conflict of interest in this study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study conducted through analysis and interpretation of data.

Profile of Respondents

The profile of student respondents is presented in Table 3. The study included a total of 137 female respondents (50.7%) and 133 male respondents (49.3%) which is an almost equal number among the total respondents. Respondents per grade level were achieved as computed previously with Grade 10 having the greatest number of students (n= 87, 32.2%), followed by Grade 9 (n = 68, 25.2%). On the other hand, the number of Grade 7 and Grade 8 students were almost the same with 57 (21.1%) and 58 (21.5%) respondents, respectively.

Table 3. Profile of Student Respondents

Profile	Frequency (n = 270)	Percentage
Sex		
Male	133	49.3%
Female	137	50.7%
Grade Level		
Grade 7	57	21.1%
Grade 8	58	21.5%
Grade 9	68	25.2%
Grade 10	87	32.2%

Table 4 presents the profile of teacher respondents. Most of the teachers have their bachelor's degree (n = 42, 95.5%). Only 2 or 4.5% of the respondents have master's degree. Most of the respondents have more than 15 years of teaching experience (n = 13, 29.5%) and those with 6-10 years of teaching (n = 12, 27.3%). These are followed by teachers with 11-15 years (n = 10, 22.7%), 1-5 years (n = 7, 15.9%), and less than 1 year of teaching experience (n = 2, 4.5%). Almost half of the respondents or 20 (45.5%) have 1-3 trainings on online learning. Twelve (12) or 27.3% of the respondents have 4-6 trainings and ten (10) or 22.7% respondents have more than 9 trainings. Only two respondents (4.5%) have 7-9 trainings.

Table 4. Profile of Teacher Respondents

Profile	Frequency (n = 44)	Percentage
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's	42	95.5%
Master's	2	4.5%
Years of Teaching		
Less than 1 year	2	4.5%
1-5 years	7	15.9%
6-10 years	12	27.3%
11-15 years	10	22.7%
More than 15 years	13	29.5%
Training on Online Learning		
1-3 trainings	20	45.5%
4-6 trainings	12	27.3%
7-9 trainings	2	4.5%
More than 9 trainings	10	22.7%

Students' Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality

Table 5. Students' Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality through Teaching Presence

Statement	TEACHING PRESENCE			
	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Rank
1. The instructor clearly communicated important topics.	3.33	0.583	Moderately Effective	3
2. The instructor clearly communicated important subject goals.	3.32	0.587	Moderately Effective	4
3. The instructor provided clear instructions to participate in subject learning activities.	3.39	0.578	Moderately Effective	2
4. The instructor clearly communicated important due dates frames for learning activities.	3.44	0.624	Moderately Effective	1
5. The instructor was helpful in identifying areas of agreement and disagreement on topics that helped me to learn.	3.28	0.630	Moderately Effective	7
6. The instructor was helpful in guiding the class towards understanding topics in a way that helped me clarify my thinking.	3.31	0.678	Moderately Effective	5
7. The instructor helped to keep students engaged and participate in productive dialogue.	3.28	0.674	Moderately Effective	8
8. The instructor helped keep the students on task in a way that helped me to learn.	3.27	0.694	Moderately Effective	9
9. The instructor encouraged students to explore new concepts.	3.30	0.691	Moderately Effective	6
10. Instructor reinforced the development of a sense of community among students.	3.24	0.720	Moderately Effective	11
11. The instructor helped to focus discussion on relevant issues in that helped me to learn.	3.27	0.739	Moderately Effective	10
12. The instructor provided feedback that helped me understand my strengths and weaknesses relative to the subject's goals and objectives.	3.09	0.804	Moderately Effective	12
13. The instructor provided feedback in a timely fashion.	2.96	0.794	Moderately Effective	13
OVER-ALL MEAN	3.27	0.464	Moderately Effective	

Legend: Highly effective = 3.51 – 4.00; Moderately effective = 2.51 – 3.50; Fairly effective = 1.51 – 2.50; Poorly effective = 1.00 – 1.51

Table 5 shows the students' assessed effectiveness of online learning modality in terms of teaching presence. All statements pertaining to teaching presence were scored as moderately effective with an over-all mean of 3.27 and SD of 0.464. Among the strongest areas of

teaching presence is that “The instructor clearly communicated important due dates frames for learning activities” with a mean score of 3.44 and SD of 0.624. This suggests that, on average, the instructor's engagement and guidance in the learning process are reasonably satisfactory. Clear communication of due dates helps students manage their time effectively. Students can efficiently plan their schedules and avoid rush on their work (Gregory & Moron-Garcia, 2009). On the other hand, the statement “The instructor provided feedback in a timely fashion” had the lowest mean score of 2.96 (SD = 0.794). This indicates that, on average, participants rated the instructor's timeliness in providing feedback below the midpoint of the scale (which typically ranges from 1 to 5). This suggests that there is room for improvement in this aspect of teaching presence according to the respondents. Moreover, the low mean score suggests that while some participants may have felt satisfied with the timeliness of feedback, others likely perceived it as less prompt. This variation in perceptions could be due to factors such as differing expectations, experiences, or interpretations of what constitutes timely feedback. Feedback is used to allow students check their current work, make necessary adjustments to that work, and bring those strategies for their future work. Delays in feedback can impact student learning and engagement as timely feedback is crucial for students to understand their performance and make necessary improvement (Moallem & Webb, 2016).

Table 6. *Students' Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality through Social Presence*

SOCIAL PRESENCE				
Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Rank
1. Getting to know other students gave me a sense of belonging in the course.	3.25	0.788	Moderately Effective	1
2. I was able to form distinct impressions of some students.	3.11	0.711	Moderately Effective	2
3. Online or web-based communication is excellent medium for social interaction.	2.83	0.928	Moderately Effective	6
4. I felt comfortable conversing through the online medium.	2.93	0.928	Moderately Effective	4
5. I felt comfortable participating in the online discussions.	2.86	0.912	Moderately Effective	5
6. I felt comfortable interacting with other students.	3.04	0.874	Moderately Effective	3
7. I felt comfortable disagreeing with other course participants while still maintaining a sense of trust.	2.80	0.819	Moderately Effective	8
8. I felt that my point of view was acknowledged by other students.	2.80	0.828	Moderately Effective	7
9. Online discussions help me to develop a sense of collaboration.	2.74	0.916	Moderately Effective	9
OVER-ALL MEAN	2.93	0.571	Moderately Effective	

Legend: Highly effective = 3.51 – 4.00; Moderately effective = 2.51 – 3.50; Fairly effective = 1.51 – 2.50; Poorly effective = 1.00 – 1.51

Table 6 shows the students' assessed effectiveness of online learning modality in terms of social presence. Like teaching presence, all statements pertaining to social presence were scored as moderately effective with an over-all mean of 2.93 and SD of 0.571. The statement “Getting to know other students gave me a sense of belonging in the course” had the highest mean score of 3.25 with SD of 0.788. The mean score of 3.25 suggests that, on average, participants agreed or strongly agreed that getting to know other students contributed positively to their sense of belonging in the course. This indicates that interpersonal connections and interactions with fellow students played a significant role in fostering a sense of belonging among the participants. Moreover, students feel a sense of connection and interaction even in the virtual or online learning environment as they get to know each other. This gives a positive and effective online learning experience among students as it builds belongingness. The academic performance of students is found to positively affected by indicators of social presence as it increased meaningful interactions among students (Joksimovic et al., 2015). As such, building opportunities for students to interact and form relationships with their peers can be a valuable strategy for promoting a sense of belonging in the course. This finding highlights the importance of fostering a supportive and inclusive learning community where students feel connected to their peers and invested in the learning experience.

Meanwhile, the lowest mean score of 2.74 with SD of 0.916 was seen in the statement “Online discussions help me to develop a sense of collaboration.” Students might feel that online discussions lack meaningful interaction and do not provide ample opportunities for collaborative learning. This entails a review of the discussion design and varied engaging teaching techniques to provide collaboration. Moreover, the majority of respondents did not perceive online discussions as particularly conducive to fostering collaboration. Technology-based learning has positive impact on student engagement and outcomes. This promotes reflection, leading to higher order thinking and higher course or subject performance (Dumford and Miller, 2018). Educators may consider strategies such as providing clearer guidelines for participation, incorporating more interactive and engaging activities, or fostering a supportive and inclusive online environment to enhance the effectiveness of online discussions in promoting collaboration among students.

Table 7 shows the students' assessed effectiveness of online learning modality in terms of cognitive presence. Like teaching and social presence, all questions pertaining to cognitive presence were scored as moderately effective with an over-all mean of 3.12 and SD of 0.492. The statement “Reflection on content and discussions helped me understand fundamental concepts in this class” had the highest mean score of 3.25 with SD of 0.646. Students recognize the value of reflecting on the course content and online discussions as an effective learning strategy. It also entails that students feel engaged in critical thinking during online reflections, allowing them to delve deeper in the fundamental concepts of the subject or course.

Table 7. *Students' Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality through Cognitive Presence*

<i>COGNITIVE PRESENCE</i>				
<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. Problems posed increased my interest in subject issues.	3.01	0.797	Moderately Effective	10
2. Online activities piqued my curiosity.	2.97	0.824	Moderately Effective	12
3. I felt motivated to explore content related questions.	2.99	0.847	Moderately Effective	11
4. I utilized a variety of information sources to explore problems posed in online class.	3.14	0.723	Moderately Effective	6
5. Brainstorming and finding relevant information helped me resolve content related questions.	3.24	0.659	Moderately Effective	2
6. Online discussions were valuable in helping me appreciate different perspectives.	3.06	0.776	Moderately Effective	9
7. Combining new information helped me answer questions raised in online activities.	3.21	0.678	Moderately Effective	4
8. Learning activities helped me construct explanations/solutions.	3.21	0.689	Moderately Effective	3
9. Reflection on content and discussions helped me understand fundamental concepts in this class.	3.25	0.646	Moderately Effective	1
10. I can describe ways to test and apply the knowledge created.	3.10	0.696	Moderately Effective	8
11. I have developed solutions to problems that can be applied in practice.	3.11	0.726	Moderately Effective	7
12. I can apply the knowledge created in the class to my work or other non-class-related activities	3.17	0.739	Moderately Effective	5
OVER-ALL MEAN	3.12	0.492	Moderately Effective	

Legend: Highly effective = 3.51 – 4.00; Moderately effective = 2.51 – 3.50; Fairly effective = 1.51 – 2.50; Poorly effective = 1.00 – 1.51

This result underscores the value of incorporating reflective practices into the teaching and learning process to deepen students' understanding of fundamental concepts and promote meaningful learning experiences. Educators may consider integrating more reflective activities into their courses and providing guidance on how to effectively engage in reflection to enhance student learning outcomes. An effective online learning environment must have both conversation and reflection, as they have the power to enhance the significance of learners' experiences. In this sense, cognitive presence can be applied as a directed paradigm to facilitate positive learning outcomes (Sadaf et al., 2021). The lowest among the statements is "Online activities piqued my curiosity" with a mean score of 2.97 and SD of 0.824. Students might find online activities not engaging or not enough to capture their interest and stimulate their curiosity. The online activities may not have been perceived as directly relevant or applicable to the students' interests. There is a need to understand and assess what matters most among students which can drive them to certain goals, motivate and ignite their curiosity in the subject area (Orcutt et al., 2017).

Table 8. *Assessed Mean Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality among Students*

<i>Parameters</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Teaching Presence	3.27	0.464	Moderately Effective	1
Social Presence	2.93	0.571	Moderately Effective	3
Cognitive Presence	3.12	0.492	Moderately Effective	2
Over-all Mean	3.11	0.529	Moderately Effective	

Legend: Highly effective = 3.51 – 4.00; Moderately effective = 2.51 – 3.50; Fairly effective = 1.51 – 2.50; Poorly effective = 1.00 – 1.51

The students assessed that online learning modality is moderately effective in all parameters measured with an over-all mean of 3.11 and SD of 0.529. Table 8 shows that teaching presence has the highest mean score of 3.27 with a standard deviation of 0.464. Teaching presence is important in achieving student learning outcomes during an online learning environment. In a student's perspective, teaching presence is an important driver of the effectiveness of online learning. The effectiveness through teaching presence is indicated by several factors such as design and organization, facilitation and direct instruction. Related to this, teaching presence is an essential predictor of students' perception of learning, satisfaction, and connectedness in an online learning environment (Gurley, 2018; Sheridan et al., 2013).

The students considered cognitive presence as an indicator of the effectiveness of online learning modality. As shown in Table 8, it has a mean score of 3.12 and an SD of 0.492. This suggests that the online learning environment experienced by students was moderately effective as supported by the effective facilitation and promotion of cognitive presence. Cognitive presence enables students and learners to construct and confirm meaning through a continuous reflection and discourse. This is also connected to the level of students' engagement in learning. As such, it is considered an important indicator of quality online education (Garrison & Akyol, 2015). The findings of the study conform with that of McKerlich et al. (2011), as cognitive presence was also highly rated as an indicator of effective online learning. Cognitive presence indicates that students are constructing meaning and connecting to knowledge.

Social presence had the lowest mean among the three parameters studied with a mean score of 2.93 and SD of 0.571. However, social presence still contributed to the effectiveness of online learning modality. Students may consider social presence as the ability to perceive others in an online learning environment. Results show that students' participation and motivation is positively influenced by social presence leading to an effective online learning. These findings related the study of Garrison and Akyol (2013) as social presence encourages students to interact even in the online classroom as it can engage learners in critical thinking and higher-level learning.

Teachers' Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality

Table 9. Teachers' Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality through Teaching Presence

TEACHING PRESENCE				
Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Rank
1. I clearly communicated important topics.	3.80	0.408	Highly Effective	3.5
2. I clearly communicated important subject goals.	3.80	0.408	Highly Effective	3.5
3. I provided clear instructions to participate in course learning activities.	3.86	0.347	Highly Effective	1
4. I clearly communicated important due dates frames for learning activities.	3.80	0.408	Highly Effective	2
5. I was helpful in identifying areas of agreement and disagreement on course topics that helped me to learn.	3.64	0.487	Highly Effective	8
6. I was helpful in guiding the class towards understanding course topics in a way that helped me clarify my thinking.	3.75	0.438	Highly Effective	5
7. I helped to keep students engaged and participate in productive dialogue.	3.68	0.471	Highly Effective	9.5
8. I helped keep the students on task in a way that helped me to learn.	3.68	0.471	Highly Effective	9.5
9. I encouraged students to explore new concepts.	3.70	0.462	Highly Effective	6.5
10. I reinforced the development of a sense of community among students.	3.68	0.471	Highly Effective	9.5
11. I helped to focus discussion on relevant issues in that helped me to learn.	3.70	0.462	Highly Effective	6.5
12. I provided feedback that helped students understand my strengths and weaknesses relative to the subject's goals and objectives.	3.68	0.471	Highly Effective	9.5
13. I provided feedback in a timely fashion.	3.59	0.497	Highly Effective	13
OVER-ALL MEAN	3.72	0.305	Highly Effective	

Legend: Highly effective = 3.51 – 4.00; Moderately effective = 2.51 – 3.50; Fairly effective = 1.51 – 2.50; Poorly effective = 1.00 – 1.51

Table 9 shows the teachers' assessed effectiveness of online learning modality in terms of teaching presence. All statements pertaining to teaching presence were scored as highly effective with an over-all mean score of 3.72 and SD of 0.305. On the statement "I provided clear instructions to participate in course learning activities," teachers scored it the highest with a mean score of 3.44 and SD of 0.624. This indicates that the teachers affirm their online teaching presence through providing clear instructions to students and let them participate in the activities. Teachers are confident in conveying expectations and guidelines for student engagement. This is essential to align learning activities with course objectives achieving outcomes from students. Moreover, the result indicates that teachers excel in providing clear and effective instructions for participating in course learning activities, which is crucial for facilitating a positive and productive learning experience for students. Providing students with course documents uploaded in online portals or with course orientations through video recordings and conferences is crucial as students may have not immediate access to teachers as may be limited by some resources (i.e., poor internet connection) (Gurley, 2018). On the other hand, the statement "I provided feedback in a timely fashion." had the lowest mean score of 3.59 with a SD of 0.4974 as perceived by teachers. According to the teachers' self-assessment, providing feedback in a timely manner received the lowest mean score among the evaluated aspects. Similar to the response of students, teachers agree that there is no timely feedback given to their students. Teachers may view feedback as a communication strategy to their students. This provides not only the grade mark but also information about how students can improve their work (Richardson et al., 2016). While teachers may acknowledge the importance of providing feedback promptly, they perceive that they may not always be meeting this expectation effectively. This finding could serve as a valuable insight for teachers to reflect on their feedback practices and consider strategies for improving the timeliness and effectiveness of their feedback delivery.

Table 10. Teachers' Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality through Social Presence

SOCIAL PRESENCE				
Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Rank
1. Getting to know students gave me a sense of belonging in the course.	3.59	0.658	Highly Effective	1
2. I was able to form distinct impressions of students.	3.39	0.689	Moderately Effective	2
3. Online or web-based communication is excellent medium for social interaction.	2.95	0.861	Moderately Effective	9
4. I felt comfortable conversing through the online medium.	3.07	0.728	Moderately Effective	8
5. I felt comfortable participating in the online discussions.	3.16	0.713	Moderately Effective	6.5
6. I felt comfortable interacting with students.	3.36	0.650	Moderately Effective	3
7. I felt comfortable disagreeing with other course participants while still maintaining a sense of trust.	3.16	0.713	Moderately Effective	6.5
8. I felt that my point of view was acknowledged by students.	3.34	0.608	Moderately Effective	4
9. Online discussions help me to develop a sense of collaboration.	3.23	0.711	Moderately Effective	5
OVER-ALL MEAN	3.25	0.575	Moderately Effective	

Legend: Highly effective = 3.51 – 4.00; Moderately effective = 2.51 – 3.50; Fairly effective = 1.51 – 2.50; Poorly effective = 1.00 – 1.51

Table 10 shows the teachers' assessed effectiveness of online learning modality in terms of social presence. Most statements pertaining to social presence were scored as moderately effective with an over-all mean of 3.25 and SD of 0.575. The statement "Getting to know other students gave me a sense of belonging in the course" had the highest mean score of 3.59 with SD of 0.658. Like students' assessment, teachers perceive to feel a sense of connection and interaction even in the virtual or online learning environment as they get to know their students. The high mean score and low variability underscore the significant impact of social interaction and

relationship-building on students' sense of belonging in the course. This finding highlights the importance of creating opportunities for students to engage with their peers, collaborate on assignments, participate in group discussions, and establish supportive networks within the learning community. Students derived a social connection and belongingness through interactions with teachers. There is a positive relationship and feelings of acceptance among teachers, especially how teachers get to know their students. This is also linked to a motivation and positive effect by having a personal identification and relatability of students with their teachers (Thacker et al., 2022). Meanwhile, the lowest mean score of 2.95 with SD of 0.861 was seen in the statement "Online or web-based communication is excellent medium for social interaction." This implies that the actual brick classroom setting is a better option for social interaction through the physical presence of students and teachers. However, recent studies conducted by Bower and Kumar (2015) conversely affirm that there is a significantly higher perception of social presence in online learning environment than face-to-face environment. Active learning in an online learning environment requires teachers to offer student support. Teachers must create a collaborative environment and cooperation to adopt positive attitudes (Molinillo et al., 2018).

Table 11. Teachers' Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality through Cognitive Presence

COGNITIVE PRESENCE				
Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Rank
1. Problems posed increased my interest in course issues.	3.34	0.568	Moderately Effective	12
2. Online activities piqued my curiosity.	3.36	0.614	Moderately Effective	11
3. I felt motivated to explore content related questions.	3.50	0.506	Moderately Effective	9
4. I utilized a variety of information sources to explore problems posed in online class.	3.57	0.501	Highly Effective	5
5. Brainstorming and finding relevant information helped me resolve content related questions.	3.60	0.542	Highly Effective	4
6. Online discussions were valuable in helping me appreciate different perspectives.	3.52	0.505	Highly Effective	8
7. Combining new information helped me answer questions raised in course activities.	3.64	0.574	Highly Effective	3
8. Learning activities helped me construct explanations/solutions.	3.73	0.500	Highly Effective	1
9. Reflection on course content and discussions helped me understand fundamental concepts in this class.	3.66	0.526	Highly Effective	2
10. I can describe ways to test and apply the knowledge created in this course.	3.55	0.548	Highly Effective	7
11. I have developed solutions to course problems that can be applied in practice.	3.55	0.589	Highly Effective	6
12. I can apply the knowledge created in the class to my work or other non-class related activities	3.50	0.664	Moderately Effective	10
OVER-ALL MEAN	3.54	0.446	Highly Effective	

Legend: Highly effective = 3.51 – 4.00; Moderately effective = 2.51 – 3.50; Fairly effective = 1.51 – 2.50; Poorly effective = 1.00 – 1.51

Table 11 shows the teachers' assessed effectiveness of online learning modality in terms of cognitive presence. Statements pertaining to cognitive presence were scored as highly effective and moderately effective with an over-all mean of 3.54 and SD of 0.446. The statement "Learning activities helped me construct explanations/solutions" had the highest mean score of 3.73 with SD of 0.500. Teachers believe that the learning activities in the online environment effectively facilitated the cognitive engagement and constructive thinking of both themselves and, presumably, their students. With an emphasis on constructivist approach, teachers perceive that the learning activities fostered a learning environment where knowledge is actively built and constructed rather than simply having received passively. Among the levels of cognitive presence, teachers have been on the resolution or highest stage to which knowledge gained is applied and tested as evident to the explanations / solutions constructed (Alzayed & Alabdulkareem, 2021). The lowest among the statements is "Problems posed increased my interest in course issues" with a mean score of 3.34 and SD of 0.568. This suggests that teachers did not find the problems or challenges presented in the course to be particularly engaging or stimulating. Providing context and demonstrating the practical implications of addressing course issues can enhance interest and engagement. Interaction between students and teachers must be highlighted and critical for adopting to the alignment of course outcomes. Quality teaching experience through aligned activities may increase interest with continuous collaboration between teachers and students (Law et al., 2019).

Table 12. Assessed Mean Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality among Teachers

Parameters	Mean	SD	VI	Rank
Teaching Presence	3.72	0.305	Highly Effective	1
Social Presence	3.25	0.575	Moderately Effective	3
Cognitive Presence	3.54	0.446	Highly Effective	2
Over-all Mean	3.50	0.492	Moderately Effective	

Legend: Highly effective = 3.51 – 4.00; Moderately effective = 2.51 – 3.50; Fairly effective = 1.51 – 2.50; Poorly effective = 1.00 – 1.51

The teachers assessed that online learning modality is highly effective in two parameters, namely, teaching presence and cognitive presence, and moderately effective in social presence. Table 12 shows that teaching presence has the highest mean score of 3.72 with a standard deviation of 0.305. How teachers teach during online classes is a caveat to effective online learning. However, student-teacher relationship must be established to understand deeper each student's need through the presence of teachers. Teaching presence

is important in an online learning environment. The role of teachers is more centered on facilitation and student support to develop competencies (Rapanta et al., 2020). An accurate pedagogical approach must also be developed as one of the key issues in the design of an effective online learning environment involving teaching presence. Individual needs must be targeted by teachers, focusing on formative assessments to enhance students' learning (Carrillo & Flores, 2020).

Cognitive presence is also an indicator of the effectiveness of online learning modality. Table 12 shows the mean score of 3.54 and SD of 0.446. This suggests that the online learning environment experienced by students was moderately effective as supported by the effective facilitation and promotion of cognitive presence.

Teachers have critical roles in guiding students for the critical thinking processes. This is an opportunity for teachers to stimulate students' analysis, synthesis, and evaluation of information. Students must reflect on learning experiences guided by teachers. Real-life scenarios may be given by teachers to be analyzed by students and identify solutions for problems identified. This is recommended to teachers for improving learning environments. Cognitive presence involves triggering event, exploration, integration and resolution (Meda & ElSary, 2021).

Social presence had the lowest mean among the three parameters studied with a mean score of 3.25 and SD of 0.575. In the case of teachers, social presence involves the establishment of connection with students. This goes beyond the delivery of content and contributes meaningfully to a supportive and engaging online learning environment. Teachers have multiple roles in facilitating classes, primarily in collaboration and social presence. The multiple roles of teachers provide different senses of student learning during online activities. The social presence of teachers dominates in shaping online educational experience for students (Szeto, 2015).

Significant Differences in the Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality among Respondents

The data gathered in each parameter was further analyzed to assess the difference of the assessed effectiveness of online learning modality among respondents when grouped according to their profile.

Table 13. *Difference in the Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality among Students' Profile*

Profile	Parameters	Mean	F	Sig	Interp.	Decision on Ho	
Grade Level	Teaching Presence	Grade 7	3.41	3.338	.020	Significant	Reject
		Grade 8	3.29				
		Grade 9	3.15				
		Grade 10	3.25				
	Social Presence	Grade 7	3.16	6.205	.001	Significant	Reject
		Grade 8	3.00				
		Grade 9	2.75				
		Grade 10	2.88				
	Cognitive Presence	Grade 7	3.28	5.875	.001	Significant	Reject
Grade 8		3.06					
Grade 9		2.95					
Grade 10		3.19					
Sex	Teaching Presence	Male	3.27	4.449	.036	Significant	Reject
		Female	3.21				
	Social Presence	Male	3.05	11.041	.001	Significant	Reject
		Female	2.82				
	Cognitive Presence	Male	3.20	6.455	.012	Significant	Reject

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 13 shows the significant difference in the assessed effectiveness of online learning modality among student respondents when grouped according to their grade level and sex. In terms of grade level, Grade 7 students had the highest mean scores for all parameters. There is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of teaching presence among students ($F = 3.338$, $p = .020$). Social presence ($F = 6.205$) and cognitive presence ($F = 5.875$) have a statistically significant difference in the mean scores with a p-value of < 0.001 . These values indicate a significant difference among the students' mean scores of their assessed effectiveness of online learning modality. As such, the null hypothesis pertaining to these differences is rejected. There is a significant difference in the students' assessed effectiveness of online learning modality when grouped according to their grade level. Thus, the effectiveness of online learning varies with the different grade level of students. These results are supported by Allen and Seaman (2015) which have indicated that different grade levels might respond differently to online learning based on their developmental stage and learning preferences.

In terms of sex, males have higher mean scores across all parameters. When compared among groups, teaching presence ($F = 4.449$), social presence ($F = 11.041$) and cognitive presence ($F = 6.455$) also have significant differences with p-values of .036, .001, and .012, respectively. As such, the null hypothesis pertaining to these differences is rejected. There is a significant difference in the students' assessed effectiveness of online learning modality when grouped according to their sex. Thus, the effectiveness of online learning varies with the sex of students. This result is congruent to the study by Chung et al. (2020) where gender had a significant effect on

online learning experience. This may be explained by the role of self-efficacy in online learning and whether there are gender differences in how students perceive their ability to succeed in a virtual learning environment.

Table 14. *Difference in the Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality among Teachers' Profile*

Profile	Parameters	Mean	F	Sig	Interp.	Decision on Ho	
Educational Attainment	Teaching Presence	Bachelor's	3.71	.352	.556	Not significant	Accept
		Master's	3.85				
	Social Presence	Bachelor's Master's	3.21 4.00	3.801	.058	Not significant	Accept
Years of Service	Teaching Presence	Bachelor's	3.52	2.284	.138	Not significant	Accept
		Master's	4.00				
		< 1 yr.	3.46				
		1-5 yrs.	3.81				
		6-10 yrs.	3.75				
	11-15 yrs.	3.69					
	> 15 yrs.	3.70					
	Social Presence	< 1 yr.	2.94	1.284	.293	Not significant	Accept
		1-5 yrs.	3.33				
6-10 yrs.		3.43					
11-15 yrs.		3.37					
> 15 yrs.	2.99						
Cognitive Presence	< 1 yr.	3.54	1.350	.269	Not significant	Accept	
	1-5 yrs.	3.75					
	6-10 yrs.	3.66					
	11-15 yrs.	3.53					
	> 15 yrs.	3.33					
Training on Online Learning	Teaching Presence	1-3	3.67	.795	.504	Not significant	Accept
		4-6	3.80				
		7-9	3.92				
		> 9	3.68				
	Social Presence	1-3	2.98	3.218	.033	Significant	Reject
		4-6	3.41				
		7-9	3.39				
		> 9	3.57				
	Cognitive Presence	1-3	3.42	.972	.415	Not significant	Accept
4-6		3.66					
7-9		3.50					
> 9		3.54					

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 14 shows the significant difference in the assessed effectiveness of online learning modality among teacher respondents when grouped according to their profile. All parameters of assessed effectiveness of online learning, teaching presence ($F = .352$), social presence ($F = 3.801$), and cognitive presence ($F = 2.284$), when grouped according to the educational attainment of teachers were not significant with p values of .556, .058, and .138, respectively. This indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the assessed effectiveness of online learning modality when grouped according to teachers' educational attainment. This means that the effectiveness of online learning modality does not vary with the different levels of educational attainment among teachers. This is supported by a study of Mailizar et al., (2020) in Indonesia among secondary school mathematics teachers where teacher's background such as educational attainment has no significant impact on online learning and teaching.

In terms of years of service, all parameters of assessed effectiveness of online learning, teaching presence ($F = .558$), social presence ($F = 1.284$), and cognitive presence ($F = 1.350$) have no significant differences with p values of .694, .293, and .269, respectively. This indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the assessed effectiveness of online learning modality when grouped according to teachers' years of service. This means that effectiveness of online learning modality does not vary with the years of service of teachers. Teachers need to adopt during pandemic crises, where it required them to change learning patterns. This entails that even long teaching teacher need to learn systems applied to online learning (Fauzi & Khusuma, 2020).

Only the assessed social presence had a significant difference based on the training on online learning ($F = 3.218$, $p = .033$). As such, the null hypothesis pertaining to this difference is rejected. There is a significant difference in the teachers' assessed effectiveness of online learning modality based on social presence when grouped according to their training on online learning. This implies that there is a notable variation in the perceived effectiveness of online learning based on the training of teachers about social presence. In practical terms, a teacher's presence in online classroom may be improved through own experiences. Moreover, the examination of teachers' profile revealed that behaviors enhance the teaching roles when the teacher shares instructional efforts and approaches which can be used for training roadmap and support to other teachers (Richardson et al., 2015). On the other hand, teaching presence ($F =$

.795) and cognitive presence ($F = .972$) have no significant differences when grouped according to training on online learning with p values of .504 and .415, respectively. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 15. *Difference of the Assessed Effectiveness of Online Learning Modality between Students and Teachers*

Parameters	Sig	Interpretation	Decision on H_0
Teaching Presence	< 0.001	Significant	Reject
Social Presence	< 0.001	Significant	Reject
Cognitive Presence	< 0.001	Significant	Reject

Table 15 shows the significant difference in the assessed effectiveness of online learning modality between teachers and students. All parameters of assessed effectiveness of online learning, teaching presence, social presence, and cognitive presence differ between teachers and students, with p values of < 0.001. This indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the assessed effectiveness of online learning modality between teachers and students. This means that the assessed effectiveness of online learning modality differs between teachers and students. Teachers may have specific expectations regarding instructional design, content delivery and assessment in the online learning environment. Students, meanwhile, assess effectiveness based on other factors, such as engagement, clarity of instructions and their overall learning experience. In terms of social presence, teachers may emphasize their role in facilitating interaction and collaboration, while students may prioritize aspects of communication and connection. Teachers may define success in cognitive presence based on achieving learning objectives and academic outcomes. Students may define success based on their overall satisfaction, sense of accomplishment, and perceived value of the learning experience. Contributing to the effectiveness of online learning, open communication between teachers and students must be continuous to aid differences in the responses. Even though there is an evident difference, teachers and students must coordinate and collaborate well to increase motivation to online learning (Alawamleh et al., 2020).

Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn based on the findings of the study: Students and teachers assessed online learning modality as an effective platform to conduct classes and other activities. Each student is considered to have individual needs to be addressed to improve learning outcomes in the online modality. Understanding these demographic profile differences can help tailor online learning experiences to meet the diverse needs of student populations. Teachers with various trainings on online learning may have distinct perspectives on the role and importance of social presence in online learning.

There is a considerable difference between the improvement of online learning modalities among students and teachers. Teachers and students may have different perspectives on what constitutes effective online learning. Communication, collaboration, and ongoing feedback between teachers and students can contribute to a more aligned understanding of the goals and outcomes of online learning experiences.

Based on the findings and conclusions made in the study, the following are hereby recommended: Encourage open communication and collaboration between teachers and students to bridge the gap in perspectives on effective online learning using centralized platforms for communication, such as discussion forums, messaging apps or virtual classroom, or creation of small group discussion.

Recognize and address the individual needs of students to improve learning outcomes in the online modality. Implement strategies for personalized learning experience. Begin by understanding students' learning profile, weaknesses, learning style and interests. Allow students to receive varied assessment methods and differentiated instruction that cater to different learning styles and preferences. Lastly, collaborate with students to develop personalized learning plans that outline goals, strategies, and resources tailored to their needs.

Provide ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers with varying levels of educational attainment and training on online learning. Training programs can focus on enhancing teaching strategies in the online environment, with an emphasis on promoting effective social presence and engagement, as proposed.

Conduct future similar studies and add other variables to explore and understand the effectiveness of online learning modality. Moreover, studies on the sustained impact of teacher training inputs on online learning outcomes may be done. Other approaches on the assessment of online learning modality may be conducted exploring the blend of pedagogy and technology, adaptive learning strategies and hybrid learning approaches.

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